

THE EFFECT OF SEAWATER EXPOSURE ON THE FATIGUE EDGE DELAMINATION GROWTH OF A CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The effect of seawater exposure on the fatigue damage development of a carbon/epoxy composite has been investigated using the edge delamination test. Seawater exposure has a significant influence on the edge failure mode. As the amount of seawater in the sample increases, the dominant crack path changes from interply to intraply cracking, but the overall growth of these crackings remains approximately the same. Microscopic examination was used to monitor the failure mechanisms. The role of seawater exposure on the damage development and strain energy release rate was demonstrated.

Keywords: carbon/epoxy composite, moisture, seawater, delamination, strain energy release rate

1. INTRODUCTION

There has been a growing interest in using fiber-reinforced polymeric composites in offshore applications¹. The long-term durability of composites however, must be characterized before their full potential can be realized in the aggressive environment of seawater, in which a composite structure is subjected to fatigue wave loading and moisture absorption. Fatigue and damage development in composites have been the subjects of many investigations in recent years². Of the several forms of damage, delamination has been identified as the most dominant in the fatigue life of fiber-reinforced composites.

The effect of moisture on the delamination is quite complex. It can be beneficial due to the relief of residual thermal curing stresses and matrix plasticization. It can also be detrimental because of the induced chemical and/or physical degradation³⁻⁵. Several investigations have examined the fatigue behavior of composites in seawater environment^{6,7}, but few have investigated the combined effect of fatigue and seawater exposure on the damage development and rate of damage growth.

In this study, results in the effect of seawater exposure on the fatigue damage development of a carbon/epoxy composite will be presented. In particular, the edge delamination growth have been examined. The difference between the damage development of the dry and pre-conditioned samples can be used to gage the effect of seawater absorption. The interlaminar strain energy release rate of the composite laminate can be used to demonstrate the stress-relieving effect of the moisture absorption and/or any possible degradation that may have been caused by seawater absorption.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1. Materials

The composite used in this investigation was the TACTIX 556 epoxy novolac resin (Dow Chemical USA) reinforced with IM-7 (Hercules, Inc.) carbon fibers. The TACTIX 556 resin is a low moisture absorption hydrocarbon epoxy novolac resin that has a dicyclopentadiene backbone. Quasi-isotropic laminates with a stacking sequence of $[45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]_S$ was supplied by Dow Chemical. The average ply thickness is 0.16 mm (0.00625 inch) and the nominal fiber volume fraction is 53%.

The sample dimension was 228.6 mm by 12.7 mm (9 inch by 0.5 inch). The average moisture content of the sample after the cutting operation is about 0.4 wt.%, as determined by the weight loss after drying at 100°C in a vacuum oven for 20 hours. No additional weight loss can be detected for longer times. The samples used in this study, however, were not dried and they were used in the as-cut condition. The as-cut sample is referred to as dry sample in this study. Sample edges were polished to facilitate examination under optical microscope.

2.2. Moisture Conditioning

Substitute seawater, referred to as seawater in this study, mixed from distilled water and a synthetic sea salt was used for moisture conditioning and wet testing. The specific gravity of the seawater was controlled to 1.025 ± 0.001 . Some of the samples were conditioned in the seawater at room temperature prior to testing. A silicone gel coating, which was later removed prior to microscope examination, was applied to the edges of these samples to minimize the diffusion and wicking through the edges.

The results of the sorption experiment is presented in Figure 1. The moisture absorption of the laminate is approximately Fickian. At saturation, the moisture content is about 0.44 wt% of the laminate, and the diffusion coefficient is $1.95 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^2/\text{sec}$ ($3.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ in}^2/\text{hr}$). Since the epoxy novolac resin is low-moisture-absorption, it took about 8 months at room temperature to reach saturation. Fickian curve calculated with these parameters are also shown in the figure as the solid line. Samples presoaked to different amount of moisture gains were used in fatigue experiments.

Figure 1. Moisture absorption profile of the carbon/epoxy laminate.

2.3. Testing Procedures

An MTS 810 servohydraulic testing machine was used in all tests. Edge delamination tests⁸ in fatigue were performed under tension-tension load-controlled mode. The maximum stress applied was 275.8 MPa (40 ksi), which was approximately 40% of the ultimate tensile strength of the laminate. The stress ratio was 0.25; the frequency was 0.1 Hz. The low frequency, which corresponds to the peak width of a typical wave loading power spectrum⁹, was selected so that the synergistic effect of fatigue and seawater exposure can be characterized in reasonable time periods. Fatigue tests were performed up to 100,000 cycles.

An environmental cell was used for wet fatigue testing. The seawater in the environmental cell was drained and refilled with freshly mixed seawater every 5,000 cycle. The testing consists of wet fatigue tests in the environment cell with dry samples and presoaked samples of 0.25%, and 0.44% (saturated) moisture gain. Dry fatigue tests were also performed with dry samples.

Modulus of the damaged sample was measured periodically by interrupting the fatigue test, removing the sample from the environmental cell if needed, and testing quasi-statically under displacement-controlled mode at 0.25 mm/min (0.01 in/min) in a low load range. The load and displacement were transferred to an X-Y plotter.

The polished edges of samples were examined using an optical microscope, which was also used to measure the length of crack on the sample edges. Crack area was measured with an ultrasonic C-scan unit. The scanned results were first reproduced and enlarged on a xerox machine. The crack area was then determined by tracing the copies at least three times on a digitizing tablet.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Laminate Elastic Property

Since the lamina elastic properties are unavailable at this time, the undamaged laminate modulus (E_0) was experimentally determined as 52.7 GPa (7.64 Msi). A moisture gain of 0.44 wt% at saturation decreases the laminate modulus about 7% to 49 GPa (7.1 Msi), also obtained experimentally.

3.2. Effect of Seawater Exposure on the Damage Development

Several forms of damage developed during fatigue cycling, and the characteristics of wet samples are different from those of dry samples. Transverse cracks first form in the 90° plies. They are usually accompanied by cracks in the -45° plies. These cracks are dominated by the fiber/matrix interfacial failure. Under the microscope, these crack are seen to follow the fiber/matrix interface. They developed rapidly and reached equilibrium in less than 30,000 cycles. The average numbers of transverse cracks for all samples are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Average number of transverse cracks at equilibrium

sample condition	test condition	cracks in 90° ply per mm (per inch)	crack in -45° ply per mm (per inch)
Dry	Dry	0.866 (22.0)	0.728 (18.5)
Dry	Wet	0.921 (23.4)	0.823 (20.9)
0.25%	Wet	0.850 (21.6)	0.583 (14.8)
0.44%	Wet	0.929 (23.6)	0.520 (13.2)

There is a decreasing trend for the transverse cracks in the -45° plies as the moisture content of the sample increases. This is reasonable since the matrix properties is more prevalent in the angle plies. The moisture softens the resin matrix, leading to a higher toughness. This observation also supports the relief of residual thermal stresses caused by the moisture-induced swelling. Even for the case with the sample soaked to a nominal weight gain of 0.25%, there is a reduction in ply cracks because the moisture is non-uniformly distributed and the moisture content is higher than nominal value in the -45° ply.

The cases of transverse cracks in the 90° plies is less clear, and there does not appear to be a trend. In counting 90° transverse cracks, inclined cracks with angle less than 60° to the ply axis are not included. A reduction in the number of transverse cracks in the 90° ply had been observed on another system even when there is a degradation of transverse tensile strength¹⁰. This is due the reduction in the in-plane normal stress resulted from the relief of residual thermal stresses caused by the moisture absorption. For the system studied here, it seems that the degrading effect is compensated by the stress relieving effect.

The edge cracking forms at the $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interface, in the 90° ply and mid-plane $90^\circ/90^\circ$ interface, and at the $0^\circ/-45^\circ$ interface. The characteristics of the edge damage pattern is different between dry and moisture-conditioned samples. For the dry fatigue tests with dry samples, the dominant mode of damage is the delamination at the $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ ply interface. These cracks are long and straight, occasionally jump to the opposite $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ ply interface through 90° transverse cracks. This is shown in Figure 2 (a). The $0^\circ/-45^\circ$ delamination, which almost always emanated from the -45° ply crack, is also present but to a lesser extent. The pattern of edge delamination is similar for dry test with dry sample and wet test with initially dry sample. The moisture obviously has little effect during fatigue cycling.

Figure 2. Damage mode switch.
 (a) $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interply cracking from dry test with dry sample
 (b) 90° intraply cracking from wet test with saturated sample.

On the other extreme, the edge cracking for the moisture-saturated samples is drastically different. The crack path has switched from the $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interply delamination to an almost entirely intraply failure in the 90° plies. The crack path is irregular, and it is either at the $90^\circ/90^\circ$ interface or within 90° plies, as shown in Figure 2 (b). The samples with intermediate moisture contents showed a crack pattern that is between the two extremes of dry test with dry sample and wet test with saturated sample. The difference in the combination of crack paths for all samples is shown in Table 2. The percentage of the $0^\circ/-45^\circ$ delamination is somewhat misleading because most of these cracks are small compared to the other two modes. The effect of moisture is clearly seen to decrease the delamination at $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ ply interface, but to increase the intraply cracking in the 90° plies.

Table 2. Delamination path characteristics

sample condition	fatigue test condition	$90^\circ/90^\circ$ or 90° (% of total)	$-45^\circ/90^\circ$ (% of total)	$0^\circ/-45^\circ$ (% of total)
Dry	Dry	20.7	41.8	37.5
Dry	Wet	15.3	44.1	40.5
0.25%	Wet	34.0	38.5	27.5
0.44%	Wet	49.6	31.6	18.8

The extent of crack growth as obtained from the through-thickness C-scan are shown in Fig. 3 as a function of fatigue cycles. The crack area (A) is normalized against the entire area (A_0). The C-scan image is a through-thickness representation of all modes of cracking. However, since the delamination at $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interface and the 90° intraply crack are always larger than the $0^\circ/-45^\circ$ delamination and all of them overlap, the C-scan image is a representation of $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ delamination and/or 90° intraply cracking. It can be seen that the extent of crack growth of moisture-conditioned samples is not worse than the dry sample. Since it took about 8 months to saturate the sample, there does not appear to be any long-term degradation.

Figure 3. Normalized crack area as a function of fatigue cycles.

3.3. Effect of Seawater Exposure on Strain Energy Release Rate

From energy standpoint, the decrease of the $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ delamination is expected. Closed-form solution of the strain energy release rate (SERR) associated with the edge delamination had been derived based on the classical laminate theory⁸. The SERR (G) is independent of the delamination size and is given by:

$$G = \frac{t}{2} \varepsilon^2 (E - E^*) \quad (1)$$

where E is the laminate modulus, E^* is the modulus of the delaminated sublaminates, ε is the strain, and t is the laminate thickness. This was later expanded to include the effects of residual thermal curing stresses and moisture swelling using ply-by-ply analysis and finite element analysis^{5, 11-13}. The effect of thermal cool-down stress from cure cycle is to raise the SERR, while the moisture tends to reduce the SERR. Neither lamina elastic properties nor hygrothermal coefficients of the system studied here are available at this time, but the experimental relationships are shown below.

$$G_{-45/90} = \frac{t}{2} \varepsilon^2 [E - (0.957 - 0.184) E_{0, dry}] \quad (2a)$$

$$G_{90/90} = \frac{t}{2} \varepsilon^2 [E - (0.949 - 0.125) E_{0, wet}] \quad (2b)$$

E^* is derived from curve fitting the data of Figure 4, in which the moduli of the damaged sample are plotted against the normalized crack area. The first two data sets were used in deriving the E^* of Equation (2a), and the last data set were used in deriving the E^* of Equation (2b). The initial drop in the modulus of about 5% is due to the transverse crackings that occurred early in the fatigue cycling. Since load-controlled fatigue tests were used here, the strain increases as the fatigue cycle increases due to the modulus reduction. The SERR is thus the initial SERR.

Strictly speaking, neither of these equations are applicable because the cracking is not purely delamination at $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interface nor is it purely at $90^\circ/90^\circ$ interface. They are used here for comparison purpose. For the case of dry fatigue test with dry sample (i.e., when $E_{0, dry} = E_{0, wet}$), the delamination is expected to occur at $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interface because the available SERR is slightly higher than that of the $90^\circ/90^\circ$ interface delamination. This can be confirmed by analysis exists in the literature^{11,12}.

Figure 4. Modulus reduction as a function of normalized crack area.

For the fatigue tests with pre-conditioned samples, the delamination at $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interface is retarded because the SERR available is less from the stress relieving effect of moisture induced swelling¹³. The data in the literature indicates this is truly the case for delamination onset⁵. But the SERR for the $90^\circ/90^\circ$ delamination also decreases when the hygrothermal effects are considered, and it is likely that the decrease in SERR percentage wise is about the same¹³ or less (calculated with assumed

lamina properties for the system studied here) for the 90°/90° delamination. Thus the delamination at 90°/90° interface can only occur when there is a degradation of the 90° ply strength caused by the moisture absorption.

The delamination mode switch observed here is very similar to that observed by Lee¹⁴ who studied the effect of different fiber type on the SERR for edge delamination onset. As the delamination switched from the straight interply failure to the zig-zag intraply failure, the SERR decreases. He concluded that the fibers with lower interfacial strength required less SERR and produced irregular intraply failure. Since there is only one composite used in this study, damage mode switch observed confirmed there is a lowering of the interfacial strength caused by the seawater absorption.

The absorption of seawater caused the degradation of the interfacial strength for the system studied here and the SERR required should be less when there is moisture present. However, the overall growth of cracking is not worse for the test with pre-conditioned sample, as shown in Figure 3. There can be two explanation for this contradiction. The first reason is that the intraply failure actually has longer cracks due to its irregularity and zig-zag pattern. It may requires more energy than the straight -45°/90° crack, even when there is degradation present. A second possible reason is that there is indication of fiber bridging for the 90° intraply failure. As observed on the specimen edges, the cracking of the -45°/90° interply failure is clean but the 90° intraply failure often produce loose fiber ends and fiber bundles. This is shown in Figure 5, in which a comparison between these two failure mode are shown.

Figure 5. Illustration of loose fiber ends and bundles from intraply cracking.
Right half: -45°/90° interply cracking ; left half: 90° intraply cracking.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

For the carbon/epoxy composite laminate studied, the seawater exposure has no adverse effect on the fatigue damage growth. Moisture tend to decrease the available strain energy release rate. Seawater exposure does cause degradation of the interfacial strength but this degradation leads to delamination mode switch. The overall damage growth resistance of pre-conditioned sample is enhanced by the seawater exposure due to a combination of moisture-induced stress relief and damage mode switch.

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